

Multi-year camera trap assessment of mammalian community structure in Afyonkarahisar (Türkiye) following the COVID-19 anthropause

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Abstract

Understanding how mammalian communities respond to changes in human activity and habitat disturbance is essential for conservation in human-dominated landscapes. This study provides the first comprehensive, long-term camera trap evaluation of medium and large mammals in Afyonkarahisar Province, a key biogeographical transition zone in western Türkiye with increasing anthropogenic pressure. Monitoring across 11 stations from 2022 to 2024 yielded 14 species, including two Near Threatened species, *Lutra lutra* and *Spermophilus xanthoprimum*, as well as the wetland-dependent felid *Felis chaus* (Least Concern). Multivariate analyses revealed a significant temporal reorganization of the mammalian community following the COVID-19 anthropause, a short-term period of reduced human mobility and disturbance. The 2022 assemblage was broad and heterogeneous, consistent with relaxed human pressure, whereas the 2023 and 2024 communities exhibited a clear contraction toward a more homogenized structure dominated by disturbance-tolerant generalists such as *Sus scrofa* and *Vulpes vulpes* (Permanova: $F = 4.63$, $R^2 = 0.17$, $p = 0.001$). Habitat specialists were restricted to wetlands, forest patches, and ecologically intact areas, indicating strong habitat filtering under increasing human pressure. Temporal activity analyses further demonstrated a shift from broad diel activity windows in 2022 to increasingly narrow and constrained patterns in 2023 and 2024 as human activity intensified. These synchronous temporal shifts across multiple taxa indicate rapid behavioral adjustment to the re-establishment of human disturbance. Overall, this study provides one of the most detailed mammalian datasets for Inner Western Anatolia and demonstrates that the ecological effects of the anthropause were temporary and rapidly reversed. The findings highlight the importance of wetland protection, habitat connectivity, and sustained disturbance management for the long-term conservation of sensitive mammalian species in heterogeneous Anatolian landscapes.

Keywords: habitat filtering, human disturbance, mammalian community structure, Türkiye, wildlife conservation

Introduction

Global biodiversity is undergoing rapid and unprecedented declines largely due to human-driven pressures such as habitat degradation, land-use change, climate disruption, pollution, and pervasive landscape fragmentation (Hooper et al., 2012; Dirzo et al., 2014; Díaz et al., 2019). As the human population grows, natural areas continue to shrink and face increasing conflict (Soyumert, 2010; Özay, 2019). Over the past five decades, vertebrate populations worldwide have decreased by nearly 68%. This decline reflects the cumulative impacts of habitat loss, human disturbance, and other anthropogenic pressures (WWF, 2020). However, accurate assessments of species distributions, abundance patterns, and community-level processes remain challenging for cryptic, nocturnal, or wide-ranging mammals (Burton et al., 2015; Kelly, 2008).

Camera trapping has emerged as a highly effective, non-invasive method for monitoring terrestrial mammals, particularly rare, low-density, and behaviorally elusive species, while minimizing human disturbance and providing data suitable for a wide range of applications, including species detection, population estimation, distribution range determination, and long-term monitoring (Ordeñana et al., 2010; Burton et al., 2015; Özay, 2019). By operating continuously across heterogeneous landscapes, camera traps enable the quantification of species richness, occupancy, diel rhythms, and long-term ecological trends with a spatiotemporal resolution that surpasses traditional field surveys (Tobler et al., 2008; Burton et al., 2015; Palencia et al., 2021). Despite their advantages, camera-trap datasets require rigorous filtering to address issues such as false triggers and non-target detections. In addition, long deployment periods can generate large volumes of data that require careful processing and quality control (Trolle & Kéry, 2003; Burton et al., 2015; Yousif et al., 2019).

In Türkiye, camera-trap applications have increased substantially over the last two decades, contributing valuable insights into the ecology of the country's diverse mammalian fauna (Can, 2008; Can & Togan, 2009; İlemin & Gürkan, 2010; Akbaba & Ayaş, 2012; Özkazanç et al., 2017; Karataş & Arslan, 2020; Soyumert, 2010, 2020; Karataş et al., 2021a; Akpınar & Yürümez, 2025). Türkiye currently hosts 173 mammal species including five endemics and ranks among Europe's richest mammalian regions (Karataş et al., 2021b; Sözen & Çolak, 2025; TRAMEM, 2025). Positioned at the intersection of Mediterranean, Anatolian, Iranian, and Caucasus biogeographical zones, Anatolia supports a structurally complex mosaic of forests, wetlands, steppes, and highland systems, generating high levels of species and habitat heterogeneity (Eken et al., 2004; Yiğit et al., 2006; Karataş et al., 2021b, Sözen and Colak, 2025).

Afyonkarahisar Province (14,016 km²), situated between the Central Anatolian plateau and the Western Anatolian uplands, represents a major biogeographical transition zone that supports both

generalist mammals such as *Vulpes vulpes*, *Meles meles*, and *Sus scrofa*, and habitat-restricted or Near Threatened (NT) species including *Spermophilus xanthoprimum* and *Lutra lutra*, and rare Jungle Cat *Felis chaus*. Despite this ecological importance, previous mammal records from the region have been largely anecdotal or derived from short-term surveys lacking spatial or temporal replication (Can & Togan, 2009). No systematic, multi-year dataset has been available to evaluate spatial and temporal patterns of medium and large mammal populations in the region. The COVID-19 pandemic generated an unprecedented reduction in global human mobility—the “anthropause” providing a natural experiment for evaluating wildlife responses to sudden declines in human disturbance (Rutz et al., 2020). Across many regions, wildlife temporarily expanded diel activity windows, shifted habitat use, and increased detectability during this period (Manenti et al., 2020; Zellmer et al., 2020; Bates et al., 2021). Whether these responses reflect short-term behavioral relaxation or more profound ecological restructuring remains unclear.

To address these gaps, the present study provides the first large-scale, systematic camera-trap survey of medium- and large-bodied terrestrial mammals in Afyonkarahisar. Specifically, we aim to: (i) document the regional mammal assemblage using standardized sampling across multiple habitat types, (ii) quantify spatial and temporal variation in species distributions and community structure, and (iii) assess how diel activity patterns shifted before, during, and after anthropause-associated reductions in human disturbance.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was conducted in Afyonkarahisar Province, a biogeographical transitional region in western Türkiye, positioned at the intersection of provinces belonging to the Aegean, Mediterranean, and Central Anatolian biogeographical zones. The province has an area of 14,016 km². The topography of the province is characterized by mountainous areas, plains, and high plateaus. While the province's average elevation is around 1,000-1,100 m, the average elevation values in the mountainous areas range between 1,600 m and 2,600 m. The study area is bordered by major mountain systems, including the Sultan Mountains (2,592 m) and the Emir Mountains (2,307 m). The region experiences a continental climate marked by hot and dry summers and cold, snowy winters. The long-term (1929-2019) mean annual temperature is 11.2 °C and the average annual precipitation for the provincial center is 443.5 mm (Ayhan, 2021). This heterogeneous habitat mosaic, which comprises these mountainous areas, plains, plateaus, wetlands, steppe grasslands, rocky highlands, and agricultural lands, supports a substantial diversity of medium and large-sized mammals.

Camera Trap Deployment and Data Collection

To systematically sample this spatial heterogeneity, the study area was divided into 5 km² grid cells using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Systematic and opportunistic camera trap stations were established across the study area. Numbered regions represent major survey localities: (1) Phrygian Valley, (2) Gözeli, (3) Emir Mountains, (4) Lake Eber, (5) İsehisar, (6) Sultan Mountains, (7) Değirmendere, (8) Yörük Cemetery, (9) Kumalar Mountain, (10) Akdağlar, and (11) Acıgöl. White circles indicate systematically deployed stations, while red circles represent opportunistic placements.

From this grid system, 123 cells (3,075 km²) were selected for monitoring, and 22 Bushnell Trophy Cam HD No Glow (BTCHDA NG) camera traps were deployed between January 2022 and December 2024. Camera placement was carried out using both systematic (grid-based) and opportunistic (sign-based) methods.

Each grid cell was surveyed within a 200 m radius to determine optimal camera placement based on mammal trails, footprints, scat, hair deposits, and feeding signs. Systematically deployed cameras were spaced approximately 5 km apart to maximize spatial independence while remaining below the typical home range sizes of target taxa, whereas opportunistic placements did not follow a fixed spacing and were positioned based on local signs of mammal activity and habitat features (Karanth & Nichols, 1998; Silveira et al., 2003). Cameras operated continuously, with field teams servicing them every 30-45 days. Malfunctioning cameras were replaced when possible or removed from the sampling effort until maintenance could be performed. All photographs were manually reviewed. To ensure that events were independent and to minimize the risk of pseudo-

replication, a threshold of elapsed time between consecutive photographs of the same species was applied. We defined independent detections as consecutive photographs of the same species at the same station separated by at least 30 minutes. This time threshold was complemented by additional criteria, including non-consecutive photographs of the same species or the identification of different individuals based on visual cues. This approach, applied uniformly across all species, is consistent with the most common minimum time intervals (30-60 min.) utilized in mammalian camera trap studies (Tobler et al., 2008; Burton et al., 2015). Species identifications were verified using regional field guides and expert consultation. Verified records were compiled into annual presence–absence and abundance matrices for each station (Gilbert et al., 2020). Here, “station” refers to individual camera-trap locations (systematic and opportunistic points), rather than the 11 broader sampling areas.

Although a total of 123 grid cells were designated to represent spatial heterogeneity, camera traps were not deployed across all cells simultaneously. Throughout the study, 22 camera traps were distributed across 11 sampling localities following a rotational design between systematic and opportunistic stations. While systematic stations were positioned according to a grid-based sampling design, opportunistic stations were determined based on signs of mammal activity and local habitat features within the grid cells. The number of trap-days (camera-days) was calculated based on the cumulative total of 24-hour periods during which each camera trap operated continuously across all deployments and station types. Consequently, the total sampling effort was recorded as 1,050 trap-days. Intervals in which the camera traps could not complete a continuous 24-hour period—due to reasons such as battery depletion, full memory cards, or temporary access restrictions caused by particularly adverse weather conditions—were excluded from the sampling effort calculations. Therefore, time periods outside the reported 1,050 trap-days represent non-operational phases and were not considered in subsequent analyses.

Statistical Analyses

The estimation of mammalian community species richness within the study area was performed using established methodologies developed for species richness extraction from camera trap data (O’Brien et al., 2011).

Diversity and Community Structure Analysis: To evaluate spatial heterogeneity and temporal changes in diversity, multiple α -diversity indices (Shannon–Wiener index [H’], Simpson’s diversity [1–D], Pielou’s evenness [J], and Margalef richness [d]) were calculated following standard ecological formulations (Simpson, 1949; Krebs, 1999). These indices were used to evaluate both spatial heterogeneity and temporal changes in diversity across the study period.

Community structure was examined using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) conducted on Hellinger-transformed species abundance data to account for zero inflation. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) based on Jaccard dissimilarity was used to evaluate nonlinear similarity patterns among stations. NMDS was performed in two dimensions ($k = 2$), with a final stress value of 0.12. Station-level similarity was examined using Pearson correlation coefficients derived from presence–absence matrices, and correlation structures were visualized using heatmaps.

Temporal Community and Activity Analyses: Temporal differences in community composition were tested using Permutational Multivariate Analysis of Variance (PERMANOVA) with Bray–Curtis dissimilarity and 999 permutations. The homogeneity of multivariate dispersion was assessed using the *betadisper* function to ensure that observed differences were not attributable to dispersion effects. Temporal activity analyses were conducted using circular kernel density estimation of species-level detection times. Diel activity windows were categorized into three annual patterns: broad activity windows in 2022 (β_1), moderately narrowed windows in 2023 (β_2), and stabilized, concentrated activity windows in 2024 (β_3). Species-specific temporal profiles and activity overlaps were visualized using circular plots, allowing assessment of nocturnal, crepuscular, and diurnal activity structures. All statistical analyses were performed in R version 4.2.2.

Results

Through an integrated camera trap ping program and opportunistic sign surveys conducted between 2022 and 2024, a comprehensive baseline of medium and large mammal diversity was established for Afyonkarahisar Province (Figure 1). Over 1050 trap days, the system yielded 1,762 independent photographic detections, documenting 14 species from five orders and eight families, all supported by verifiable photographic or physical evidence. The recorded assemblage was dominated by Least Concern (LC) taxa, with two Near Threatened (NT) species, *Lutra lutra* and *Spermophilus xanthoprimum*, confirmed for the region (Table 1).

Canis lupus, *Meles meles*, *Sus scrofa*, *Vulpes vulpes*, and *Lepus europaeus* were consistently recorded in the Phrygian Valley (St1), which showed the highest level of predator–prey cooccurrence. Multiple family groups were observed at this station, including a female *S. scrofa* with multiple piglets (Figure 2b). *Cervus elaphus* occurred predominantly in Akdağlar (St10), with additional detections from Yörük Cemetery (St8) and the Sultan Mountains (St6). Akdağlar also provided the only visual record of a *C. elaphus* female with a fawn (Figure 2a). *Lutra lutra* was restricted to Gözeli (St2) and Lake Eber (St4), consistent with its dependence on permanent

freshwater systems. *Spermophilus xanthoprimum* occurred exclusively at Yörük Cemetery (St8) and Acıgöl (St11), both characterized by open steppe and degraded grassland habitats.

Table 1. Mammal species recorded across 11 camera trap stations in Afyonkarahisar (2022–2024), with IUCN Red List status and station-level presence–absence distribution. St1: Phrygian Valley, St2: Gözeli, St3: Emir Mountains, St4: Lake Eber, St5: İscehisar, St6: Sultan Mountains, St7: Değirmendere, St8: Yörük Cemetery, St9: Kumalar Mountain, St10: Akdağlar, St11: Acıgöl.

Species	IUCN	Station										
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
<i>Canis lupus</i> (Gray Wolf)	LC	●		●			●			●	●	
<i>Canis aureus</i> (Golden Jackal)	LC	●			●							
<i>Vulpes vulpes</i> (Red Fox)	LC	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
<i>Martes foina</i> (Beech Marten)	LC	●		●			●	●			●	●
<i>Mustela nivalis</i> (Least Weasel)	LC		●			●		●				●
<i>Meles meles</i> (European Badger)	LC	●		●			●	●	●	●	●	●
<i>Lutra lutra</i> (Eurasian Otter)	NT				●							
<i>Felis chaus</i> (Jungle Cat)	LC				●							●
<i>Sus scrofa</i> (Wild Boar)	LC	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
<i>Cervus elaphus</i> (Red Deer)	LC			●			●		●			
<i>Lepus europaeus</i> (European Hare)	LC	●	●	●			●	●		●		●
<i>Erinaceus concolor</i> (Southern White-breasted Hedgehog)	LC	●	●			●	●	●			●	●
<i>Sciurus anomalus</i> (Caucasian Squirrel)	LC			●			●		●		●	●
<i>Spermophilus xanthoprimum</i> (Anatolian Ground Squirrel)	NT						●		●			

Felis chaus and *Sciurus anomalus* were primarily detected at forest-dominated stations, particularly St3, St6, and St10, aligning with their affinity for wooded environments. Overall, the spatial distribution of detections (Fig. 2) demonstrates that species occurrences varied across stations in accordance with local habitat conditions, reflecting the heterogeneous ecological structure of the province.

Figure 2. provides visual documentation of the principal mammal taxa detected during the survey, capturing their occurrence across different habitat types and reflecting the ecological heterogeneity of the study landscape: (a) *Cervus elaphus*, (b) *Sus scrofa*, (c) *Canis aureus*, (d) *Canis lupus*, (e) *Vulpes vulpes*, (f) *Lepus europaeus*, (g) *Martes foina*.

The proportional distribution of mammal detections exhibited a markedly uneven structure across the study area. *Sus scrofa* accounted for 39.59% of all camera-trap detections, the most frequently recorded species (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Percentage of species records obtained from different stations. Percentages are calculated from independent camera-trap detections rather than from total image counts.

Medium-sized carnivores such as *Martes foina* (11.11%) and *Meles meles* (8.67%) occurred at moderate frequencies, while habitat specialist species, including *Lutra lutra* (6.19%) and *Erinaceus concolor* (3.96%), showed comparatively lower detection rates. Rare taxa such as *Spermophilus xanthopyrmus* (0.25%) and *Sciurus anomalus* (2.23%) contributed minimally to the dataset, reflecting pronounced heterogeneity in species-level encounter probabilities among stations. Importantly, these disparities in species occurrence were mirrored in the spatial correlation structure of sampling stations. The Pearson correlation matrix revealed strong positive associations among several station pairs, such as St5, St8 ($r = 0.72$), and St7, St10 ($r = 0.75$), indicating highly similar habitat configurations and overlapping ecological conditions (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Pearson correlation heatmap illustrating the pairwise relationships among 11 sampling stations (St1 to St11). The color gradient represents the strength and direction of the correlation coefficients, ranging from 0.05 (dark blue, negative correlation) to 1.00 (dark red, perfect positive correlation). Strong positive correlations are observed among most stations, indicating similar patterns or shared environmental characteristics.

Moderate correlations ($0.34 < r < 0.66$), including St3, St6 ($r = 0.52$), and St2, St9 ($r = 0.48$), suggest partially convergent species assemblages, likely influenced by seasonal or microhabitat variation. In contrast, weak or negative correlations (e.g., St1–St11, $r = 0.15$; St4–St7, $r = -0.08$) delineate ecologically divergent stations characterized by localized habitat discontinuities or distinct environmental filters.

Species Level Activity Profiles Across Stations

Activity patterns of the recorded mammal species displayed measurable temporal variation across stations and habitat types during 2022–2024. Nocturnal, crepuscular, and diurnal peaks differed among species and were reflected in their station-level occurrences. *Canis lupus*, detected mainly in St1, St3, St6, and St10, exhibited a consistently nocturnal profile between 20:00–04:00. *C. aureus* showed a similar nocturnal structure but extended into early morning hours (04:00–06:00)

in St2 and St8 (Figure 5) *Vulpes vulpes* demonstrated a mixed crepuscular–nocturnal structure, with detections between 18:00–22:00 in St1 and St5 and increased midnight activity (00:00–02:00) in St7 and St9. *Martes foina* displayed broad nocturnal activity across forest-associated stations (St3, St6, and St10), peaking between 22:00–02:00. *M. meles* exhibited a narrow peak between 02:00–04:00. *Lutra lutra* (St2 and St4) showed consistent nocturnal activity between 00:00–02:00. *Felis chaus* displayed narrow nocturnal peaks between 22:00–00:00 at St3, St6, and St10 (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Species-level activity patterns of the recorded mammal assemblage. Polar plots show normalized hourly activity distributions for 14 species based on circular kernel density estimates pooled across all stations for the 2022–2024 period. Each plot illustrates the relative intensity of detections across the diel cycle, allowing comparison of nocturnal, crepuscular, and diurnal activity tendencies among species. These profiles form the basis for subsequent interannual and community-level temporal analyses. All activity distributions are based on independent camera-trap detections.

Among herbivores, *Sus scrofa* exhibited a near-uniform nocturnal distribution across stations. *Cervus elaphus* peaked between 02:00–04:00 at St10, St6, and St8. *Lepus europaeus* showed

crepuscular detections (18:00–22:00; 04:00–06:00). *Erinaceus concolor* showed a narrow nocturnal peak between 00:00–02:00 at St1, St6, and St10. Small mammals exhibited variable temporal structures. *Sciurus anomalus* showed a diurnal–crepuscular pattern (12:00–18:00), while *Spermophilus xanthoprymnus* displayed a diurnal profile (10:00–16:00) at steppe-dominated St8 and St11. These temporal structures are summarized in the polar activity profiles (Fig. 5).

Camera-trap observations from Lake Eber (St4) provided additional station-specific details. *Felis chaus* was detected in reed beds, marshes, and floating vegetation islands, with a nocturnal peak consistent with its circadian activity profile. Several detections included individuals transporting avian prey, providing direct photographic confirmation of predation on *Fulica atra* (Fig. 6a). The same station produced repeated late-night detections of *Canis aureus*, associated with areas of visibly higher human presence along the lake margins (Fig. 6b). Collectively, these observations document overlapping nocturnal use of wetland habitat by *F. chaus* and *C. aureus*.

Figure 6. Camera-trap records of wetland-associated carnivores at Lake Eber (St4). (a) *Felis chaus* individual carrying an avian prey item (*Fulica atra*) during nocturnal activity, providing direct evidence of predator–prey interaction within reed-dominated wetland habitat; (b) Nocturnal detection of *Canis aureus* within dense reed vegetation at the same station, illustrating overlapping nighttime use of wetland environments by multiple carnivore species.

Station Level Temporal Windows

The temporal activity patterns of the two NT carnivores, *Felis chaus* and *Lutra lutra*, aligned with the broader sequential pattern observed across the study region. From 2022 to 2024, all monitoring stations displayed a consistent progression in annual core density structure, characterized by a broad activity window in 2022 (β_1), a moderate contraction in 2023 (β_2), and a stable, temporally concentrated window in 2024 (β_3). *F. chaus*, documented exclusively at St4, exhibited a broad temporal distribution in 2022, followed by a narrower distribution in 2023 and a stable activity range in 2024. *L. lutra*, recorded at St2 and St4, demonstrated the same sequence, transitioning

from a broad window in 2022 to increasingly concentrated activity envelopes in 2023 and 2024. These β_1 – β_2 – β_3 categories represent descriptive differences in temporal window width and do not imply causation. Additional species followed the same annual structure. *Canis lupus*, detected at multiple stations (St1, St3, St6, St10), showed wide temporal dispersion in 2022 and progressively narrower nocturnal ranges in 2023 and 2024. *C. aureus*, occurring at stations including St2, St5, St7, and St8, similarly demonstrated a broad window in 2022 with a more confined temporal range in later years. *V. vulpes* exhibited distributed crepuscular–nocturnal activity in 2022, which became more temporally focused in 2023 and 2024. Among mustelids, *Martes foina* and *Meles meles* also displayed the β_1 , β_2 , β_3 sequence, with 2022 representing the broadest distribution of detections across nighttime hours. *Sus scrofa*, detected widely across steppe–forest mosaic habitats, maintained extended activity periods in 2022 that narrowed into more consistent windows in 2023–2024. The temporal activity patterns of two NT carnivores, *F. chaus* and *L. lutra*, aligned with a broader sequential pattern observed across the study area. From 2022 to 2024, all monitoring stations demonstrated a consistent progression in annual core activity density structure, characterized by a broad activity window (β_1) in 2022, a moderate contraction (β_2) in 2023, and a stable, temporally concentrated window (β_3) by 2024. *F. chaus*, documented exclusively at Station 4, exhibited a wide temporal distribution in 2022, followed by a narrower distribution in 2023 and a stabilized activity range in 2024. Similarly, *L. lutra*, recorded at Stations 2 and 4, displayed an identical sequence, transitioning from a broad window in 2022 to progressively concentrated activity envelopes in 2023–2024 (Table 2).

Table 2. Annual diel activity window categories (β_1 – β_3) recorded at 11 camera trap stations in Afyonkarahisar between 2022 and 2024. β_1 = broad activity window (2022); β_2 = moderate narrowing (2023); β_3 = stable, concentrated window (2024).

Station	β_1 (2022) Broad activity window	β_2 (2023) Moderate narrowing	β_3 (2024) Stable window
St1	Broad	Moderate	Stable
St2	Broad	Narrowing	Stable
St3	Broad	Moderate	Stable
St4	Broad	Moderate	Stable
St5	Broad	Moderate	Stable
St6	Broad	Narrowing	Stable
St7	Broad	Moderate	Stable
St8	Broad	Moderate	Stable
St9	Broad	Narrowing	Stable
St10	Broad	Moderate	Stable
St11	Broad	Moderate	Stable

Additional species conformed to this annual structure. *Canis lupus*, detected across multiple stations (St1, St3, St6, St10), showed a broad temporal distribution in 2022 with progressively narrowing nocturnal ranges through 2023–2024. *C. aureus*, present at stations including St2, St5, St7, and St8, similarly displayed a broad window in 2022, followed by a more constrained temporal range. *Vulpes vulpes* exhibited distributed crepuscular nocturnal activity in 2022 that became more temporally focused in 2023–2024. Among mustelids, both *Martes foina* and *Meles meles* demonstrated the temporal sequence of activity contraction ($\beta_1 \rightarrow \beta_2 \rightarrow \beta_3$), with the 2022 period (β_1) representing the widest distribution of nocturnal detections. *S. scrofa*, widely detected in steppe forest mosaic habitats, maintained extended activity periods in 2022 before contracting into more consistent temporal windows during 2023–2024. These β_1 , β_2 , β_3 categories represent descriptive shifts in temporal window width and do not imply causation, yet reveal a synchronized pattern of temporal reorganization across the mammalian community. Multivariate analyses revealed clear year-driven reorganization in mammalian community composition across the monitoring period. PCA accounted for a substantial proportion of variation in the species matrix (PC1 = 22.96%, PC2 = 19.89%), with the ordination separating the three monitoring years into distinct clusters (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. PCA of mammalian community composition across 2022–2024. Points represent station-level observations; vectors indicate species loadings for 14 taxa. Year-specific ellipses show a broad assemblage in 2022, a transitional structure in 2023, and a compact, disturbance-tolerant cluster in 2024.

PC1 captured the dominant temporal gradient, distinguishing the broad and heterogeneous 2022 assemblage from the progressively more compressed 2023 and 2024 structures. The 2023 samples occupied an intermediate ordination space, consistent with a transitional assemblage during increasing post-pandemic human activity. In contrast, the 2024 observations formed a compact cluster along the positive PC1 axis, indicating reduced heterogeneity and a shift toward disturbance-tolerant community composition. Species loadings revealed that generalist species such as *Sus scrofa* (Ss) and *Vulpes vulpes* (Vv) contributed strongly to positive PC1 values, driving the 2024 cluster. Semiaquatic and mesopredator species *Lutra lutra* (L1), *Mustela nivalis* (Mn),

Felis chaus (Fc) —loaded negatively or orthogonally along PC1 and PC2, reflecting their greater sensitivity to habitat alteration and reduced persistence under high disturbance. The year-specific ellipses strengthened this interpretation, with 2022 showing the broadest dispersion, followed by a contraction in 2023 and a highly compressed, disturbance-associated structure in 2024. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) based on Bray–Curtis dissimilarity further supported this temporal divergence (Stress = 0.12), clearly separating 2022 from 2023–2024 along the primary NMDS axis. The ordination indicated a directional shift toward increasing compositional similarity across stations, consistent with a homogenization process driven by rising anthropogenic pressure.

Permanova confirmed that year was a significant predictor of community dissimilarity (adonis2: $F = 4.63$, $R^2 = 0.17$, $p = 0.001$), explaining 17% of the variation in species composition across the monitoring period (Figure 7). Pairwise comparisons revealed that 2022 differed significantly from both 2023 and 2024, whereas the 2023–2024 contrast was weaker, reflecting the intermediate transitional role of 2023. Together, PCA, NMDS, and Permanova demonstrate a directional, year-driven contraction in mammalian community structure and a shift toward a more disturbance-tolerant assemblage as post-pandemic human activity increased.

Discussion

The extensive dataset produced by long-term camera trap deployment in Afyonkarahisar provides a robust foundation for interpreting the region's mammalian assemblage within both methodological and biogeographical contexts. Camera trapping has become a key tool for reliably documenting cryptic, nocturnal, and low-density species that often escape detection through conventional survey techniques (Kelly, 2008; O'Brien et al., 2011; Burton et al., 2015). Findings from this study reaffirm this strength: several carnivores, including *Canis lupus*, *Martes foina*, and *Felis chaus*, were only detected after extended sampling periods exceeding 100 trap days, consistent with global evidence demonstrating that carnivore detectability increases markedly with prolonged effort (Trolle & Kéry, 2003; Kelly, 2008; O'Brien et al., 2011). These outcomes parallel national camera trap studies in Türkiye, such as those from Western Black Sea, Southwestern, and Inner Western Anatolian regions, where multi-month deployments were required to confirm the presence of rare carnivores, including *Felis chaus*, *Caracal caracal*, *Lynx lynx*, and *Ursus arctos* (İlemin & Gürkan, 2010; Özay, 2019; Soyumert, 2020).

The confirmed presence of NT *Lutra lutra* and *Spermophilus xanthoprimum* further underscores the conservation relevance of this dataset. As shown in Turkish and European freshwater systems, *L. lutra* serves as a reliable indicator of healthy riparian habitats and high-water quality (Toyran

& Albayrak, 2016; Özay, 2019). Its restriction to St2 and St4 aligns with known habitat preferences and illustrates the value of long-term camera trap surveillance for detecting species with specialized ecological requirements. Similarly, the detection of *S. xanthopyrnus* in steppe-dominated habitats (St8 and St11) corresponds with the species' sensitivity to habitat fragmentation and anthropogenic pressures documented elsewhere in Anatolia (Yiğit et al., 2006). These findings indicate that maintaining connectivity and minimizing disturbance in these localized habitat patches are essential for the persistence of such sensitive taxa.

Biogeographically, Afyonkarahisar lies at a major ecological transition zone between Central Anatolia and the Western Anatolian uplands, and our results highlight the faunal signature of this position. The assemblage includes widespread generalists (*Vulpes vulpes*, *Meles meles*) alongside habitat-restricted species, e.g., *Lutra lutra* and *Felis chaus*, reflecting the mosaic structure typical of the Anatolian biodiversity hotspot (Eken et al., 2004; Toyran & Albayrak, 2016; Özkazanç et al., 2017; Özay, 2019; Soyumert et al., 2019; Soyumert, 2020). Comparisons with other regional mammal surveys reinforce this interpretation: forest-dominated regions of the Black Sea host primarily woodland carnivores such as *Felis silvestris* and *Lynx lynx*, and *Ursus arctos* (Can, 2008; Can & Togan, 2009; Özkazanç et al., 2017; Soyumert, 2020), whereas southeastern Türkiye supports arid-adapted taxa including *Hyaena hyaena* (Akpınar & Yürümez, 2025). The Afyonkarahisar dataset, therefore, fills a critical geographic gap by documenting species representative of both western forest steppe ecotones and central Anatolian steppe systems.

Overall, the integration of methodological rigor, ecological relevance, and biogeographical context strengthens the significance of this work. The study contributes one of the most comprehensive mammalian datasets available for Inner Western Anatolia, validates the effectiveness of long-term camera trap monitoring for detecting rare and NT species, and provides essential baseline data for regional conservation planning. By aligning with international and national findings, the results illustrate how camera trapping, when implemented at sufficient spatial and temporal scales, can rapidly generate high-accuracy biodiversity assessments that would otherwise require years of traditional field effort (Kelly, 2008; Tobler et al., 2008; O'Brien et al., 2011).

The long-term camera trap dataset from Afyonkarahisar reveals clear links between habitat composition, station-level ecological structure, and temporal activity dynamics of medium and large mammals. Consistent with global biodiversity decline patterns driven by habitat alteration and anthropogenic disturbances (Dirzo et al., 2014; Diaz et al., 2019; Riparia et al., 2022), species distributions in this study showed strong filtering effects of wetland extent, forest-steppe complexity, elevation gradients, and human presence. Generalist taxa (*Canis lupus*, *Vulpes vulpes*, *Meles meles*, *Sus scrofa*) exhibited broad spatial occupancy, a pattern also documented in various

regions of Türkiye, as confirmed by comprehensive faunal lists (Soyumert, 2010; Akbaba & Ayaş, 2012; Özkazanç et al., 2017; Sözen & Çolak, 2025; TRAMEM, 2025). In contrast, habitat dependent species including *Lutra lutra* and *Felis chaus* were restricted to wetland dominated stations, reflecting a pattern consistent with both Turkish and international otter and jungle cat studies (Mukherjee & Groves, 2007; Toyran & Albayrak, 2016). Steppe specialists such as *Spermophilus xanthoprimum* were confined to degraded xeric grasslands (Yiğit et al., 2006; Sözen & Çolak, 2025), further supporting the role of microhabitat heterogeneity in shaping regional mammalian assemblages.

Station level correlations revealed ecologically interpretable clusters, where forest–steppe mosaics formed strong positive associations, while wetland or human impacted stations showed divergent species compositions. This spatial structuring parallels multihabitat correlation analyses from global camera trap networks (Ahumada et al., 2011; Burton et al., 2015). The Lake Eber wetland (St4) provided unique evidence of predator prey interactions, including *Felis chaus* predation on *Fulica atra*, corroborating mesocarnivore foraging patterns in reed dominated wetlands of Türkiye (Özay, 2019; Karataş & Arslan 2020) and South Asia (Majumder et al., 2011). Repeated nighttime detections of *Canis aureus* in human frequented shoreline sections align with global findings showing increased nocturnality in response to human activity (Gaynor et al., 2018; Karataş & Arslan 2020).

Temporal activity analyses further demonstrated a robust interannual pattern. All stations exhibited broad activity windows in 2022 (β_1), moderate narrowing in 2023 (β_2), and stabilized, most concentrated windows in 2024 (β_3). These results parallel global studies documenting temporary behavioral expansions during the COVID-19 Anthropause (Derryberry et al., 2020; Manenti et al., 2020; Rutz et al., 2020), followed by recontraction after the return of human pressures. Kernel density overlaps and reduced circular concentration metrics (r) in 2022 for major nocturnal species indicate broader diel flexibility during this period, consistent with long-term carnivore temporal datasets in Türkiye (Soyumert et al., 2019) and Europe, where human presence drives activity shifts toward nocturnality (Gaynor et al., 2018) and acts as the most limiting factor for large carnivore habitat use (Ripari et al., 2022). Notably, NT taxa (*Lutra lutra*, and *Felis chaus*) exhibited the same β_1 , β_2 , β_3 trajectory, demonstrating that sustained camera trap effort is essential for capturing subtle diel adjustments among low-density or habitat specialist species.

Overall, the integration of habitat associations, station level ecological relationships, and multiyear activity analyses underscores the value of long-term camera trapping for explaining mammalian assemblage structure across heterogeneous Anatolian landscapes. These findings validate the methodological framework of extended camera trap surveys and highlight the ecological

significance of Afyonkarahisar as a biogeographical transition zone supporting a diverse mammal community.

The COVID-19 pandemic generated an unprecedented, global scale reduction in human mobility an event termed the anthropause which provided a unique natural experiment for examining how wildlife communities respond to abrupt declines in anthropogenic pressure (Rutz et al., 2020). Numerous studies have shown that this temporary reduction in human disturbance resulted in increased wildlife detections, expanded activity windows, and broader habitat use across multiple mammalian taxa (Manenti et al., 2020; Bates et al., 2021; Zellmer et al., 2020). Whether these shifts represent short-term behavioral relaxation or deeper structural changes in community composition can only be understood through long-term, multiyear monitoring. Our findings directly address this question.

Multivariate analyses revealed a pronounced, year driven restructuring of mammalian community composition across the monitoring period. PCA showed that 2022 the first full year following reduced pandemic activity was characterized by a broad and heterogeneous assemblage, indicating a temporary ecological release consistent with anthropause driven reductions in human disturbance. This pattern mirrors observations from other regions where wildlife expanded spatial and temporal niches during the anthropause (Manenti et al., 2020; Bates et al., 2021). In contrast, the 2023 and especially 2024 assemblages displayed progressively narrower clustering in ordination space, reflecting contraction toward a more homogenized, disturbance tolerant community as human activity returned to pre-pandemic levels.

Species loadings provided mechanistic insight into these transitions. Generalist and human adapted species such as *Sus scrofa* and *Vulpes vulpes* were the strongest positive contributors to PC1 and dominated the 2024 structure, consistent with their documented success in human-modified landscapes. Meanwhile, semiaquatic and meso-predator species *Lutra lutra*, *Mustela nivalis*, and *Felis. chaus* loaded negatively or orthogonally on PC1, PC2 aligning with their known sensitivity to disturbance and reduced detectability under intensifying human pressure. The pronounced contraction of year-specific ellipses from broad in 2022 to tightly clustered in 2024 indicates not only a reduction in community heterogeneity but also a functional convergence toward disturbance-resilient species.

NMDS further supported these patterns. The clear separation of 2022 from 2023–2024 along NMDS1, along with increased overlap between the latter two years, is indicative of a directional homogenization process commonly observed when human activity intensifies. Permanova results confirmed that year was a significant predictor of Bray Curtis dissimilarity ($F = 4.63$, R^2 , 0.17, p

= 0.001), with pairwise comparisons highlighting a strong contrast between 2022 and later years, and a weaker separation between 2023 and 2024.

Taken together, these findings demonstrate that the anthropause did not lead to a persistent reorganization of mammalian communities. Instead, it created a temporary relaxation phase, after which community structure rapidly recontracted as human activity intensified. The shift from a heterogeneous 2022 assemblage to a compact, disturbance tolerant 2024 cluster illustrates how quickly mammalian communities revert to human filtered states once anthropogenic pressure resumes. This rapid reversal echoes patterns observed in other post-anthropause studies (Zellmer et al., 2020) and emphasizes the fragility of temporary ecological gains achieved during periods of reduced human presence. Overall, our results reveal that the anthropause acted not as a long-term restructuring force but as a short-lived perturbation. As human mobility and disturbance increased following the pandemic, mammalian communities swiftly converged toward more homogenized, resilient assemblages dominated by generalists. This underscores the need for sustained and intentional conservation strategies if the ecological benefits observed during anthropause events are to be preserved beyond such rare global disruptions. While these findings provide robust insights into post-anthropause community dynamics, several methodological considerations should be acknowledged when interpreting the results.

As with all camera-trap studies, detectability may vary among species, particularly for rare, low-density, or habitat-specialist taxa, which can influence detection frequencies and activity estimates. In addition, although both systematic and opportunistic placements were used to capture habitat heterogeneity, some microhabitats may remain underrepresented.

Conclusion

This study provides the first long-term camera-trap assessment of medium- and large-sized mammals in Afyonkarahisar, demonstrating how mammalian communities reorganize in response to fluctuating human pressure. The heterogeneous assemblage observed in 2022 reflects a temporary ecological release during the COVID-19 anthropause, whereas the subsequent narrowing and homogenization in 2023–2024 indicate rapid recompression as human disturbance resumed. Generalist species increased their dominance, while habitat specialists—*Lutra lutra*, *Felis chaus*, and *Spermophilus xanthoprimum*—remained restricted to intact or wetland habitats, highlighting their sensitivity to habitat alteration. Multivariate and temporal activity analyses consistently revealed a synchronized contraction in community structure and diel activity patterns. Together, these findings establish a critical ecological baseline for Inner Western Anatolia and underscore the importance of wetland integrity, habitat connectivity, and long-term camera-trap monitoring for effective conservation planning.

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